

GROSS OSTEOMORPHOMETRICAL STUDIES ON THE TIBIA AND FIBULA OF THE LEOPARD (*Panthera pardus*)

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Abstract

Effective law enforcement and the preservation of biodiversity are seriously threatened by the illegal wildlife trade, especially bones of wild animals particularly leopard bones. Identification of seized leopard bones frequently impedes forensic investigations and convictions because to a lack of osteological data. In order to support wildlife forensic identification, this study records the osteological data and gross morphological characteristics of the tibia and fibula of the leopard (*Panthera pardus*). Standard osteometric methods were used to record precise measures. The tibia and fibula were long bones with a noticeable interosseous gap that were united at both extremities. Unique morphological traits were noted, offering trustworthy diagnostic criteria useful for conservation and animal forensic investigations.

Key words: leopard, tibia and fibula, gross morphology, osteomorphometry

Introduction

India is blessed with rich biodiversity with variety of fascinating wild flora and fauna. In recent years, India is now playing a pivotal role in the trade of wild animals and has become an exporter and a conduit for wildlife (Menon and Kumar, 1999). Apart from various threats like loss of habitat, poisoning, accident and diseases facing wildlife today for its survival, poaching remains an important cause for wildlife extinction. Poaching of wild animals, particularly of leopard for bone trade has been increased recently and it is six to seven times greater than tigers (Menon and Kumar, 1999). In Chinese Myth, bones are used to manufacture traditional medicine for treating various ailments. These are sold then clandestinely in Far East and many western countries. Due to this unfortunately, these species are at the verge of extinction and need immediate action against poachers.

The forensic science forms a vital part of the entire justice and regulatory system. Forensic scientists may be involved in all aspects of a poaching case, and the results of their work may serve either for the defense or for the prosecution (Podhade, 2007). The forensic scientist's skill is to use all the information available to determine facts.

The trade of bones in wild animals is multi-million-dollar business. From small-time poaching and hunting, it has grown into a well-organized, sophisticated network of racketeers across the world, which carry out a trade ring worth an estimated 6 to 20 billion dollars worldwide. Sadly, as the international wildlife trade has increased and becomes more lucrative, wildlife-rich nations have been unable to control the trade of their wildlife. Although there are laws in place that prohibit the killing and trade of wild fauna.

Biological materials including bones of wild animals are sent routinely to State Diagnostic or Forensic Laboratories for identification of species. Due to lack of systemic studies Veterinarians by and large remain ignorant of such information. Moreover, lack of scientific documentation of characteristics, consequently the custodian of wild animals faces embarrassment at many times, when some forensic cases require scientific record for legal proceedings against the poacher and trader.

Information on bones of leopard is meager. Therefore, the identification of seized bones becomes extremely difficult. Due to lack of information, identification of bones of leopard has been bottleneck in convictions of poachers. Thus, there is an urgent need for the systematic and scientific studies on gross morphological bone structure of leopard. Hence, study is done to document gross morphological features and osteological parameters of tibia and fibula of the leopard.

Material and methods

The present work was conducted on gross morphological features and osteological parameters of tibia and fibula of the four leopard in the School of Wildlife Forensic and Health, N.D.V.S.U., Jabalpur. The

various parameters of tibia and fibula of the leopard were recorded with the help of Vernier caliper/ thread / scale in cm. Weight was taken with the help of electronic balance machine. The data collected were analyzed for mean and standard error as per the standard procedure of Panes and Sukhatme (1967) and Snedecor and Cochran (1967).

Result and Discussion:

The tibia and fibula of the leopard were long bones fused at the proximal and distal extremities creating an extensive interosseous space tallied with the findings of Onwuama et al (2021) in lion. Tibia was larger than the fibula. The total mean length of tibia was 22.72 ± 0.70 cm. It had a shaft and two extremities.

The shaft of the tibia was prismatic at its upper two third and cylindrical at its lower third (Fig. No. 01) resembled with that of tiger (Pandit, 1994). The mean circumference of the shaft was 9.62 ± 0.47 cm, 6.67 ± 0.15 cm and 6.62 ± 0.92 cm at its upper, middle and lower part respectively (Table.01). Medial surface of the shaft was rough and slightly concave close to the proximal extremity and smooth and straight distally. Lateral surface was smooth and deeply concave at its upper fourth straight in its distal 3/4th. Caudal surface was straight and had two distinct oblique popliteal lines in its upper half (Fig. No. 01). Nutrient foramen was present on the upper fourth of the caudal surface very close to the lateral border.

The proximal extremity of the tibia was much larger than the distal extremity. The mean circumference and width of the proximal extremity was 14.00 ± 0.41 cm and 4.65 ± 0.14 cm respectively (Table. 01). It was comprised of medial and lateral condyles as reported by Getty (1975) in horse and Ray and Ray (1994) in leopard. The mean length of the medial condyle (3.32 ± 0.12 cm) was more than the lateral condyle (2.97 ± 0.08 cm) whereas mean width of medial condyle (1.70 ± 0.10 cm) was less than the lateral condyle (1.92 ± 0.12 cm) (Table. 01). The intercondyloid eminences (medial and lateral) were of more or less of same height. The free edge of medial eminence was sharp while that of lateral one was blunt. In front of the lateral condyle, there was a large elliptical smooth area (Plate.01). Such area was absent in front of the medial condyle. Cranial part of proximal extremity presented tibial tuberosity, which was rough at its upper part and smooth at its lower part (Plate. 01). Sulcus muscularis on the cranial aspects of the lateral condyle was shallow. Popliteal notch was distinct on the caudal aspect of the proximal extremity between two condyles and resembled with that of tiger, Pandit (1994). The tibial spine was a central articular eminence divided into a medial higher and a lateral lower part in the leopard as described by Raghavan (1964) in ox and Choudhary *et al.* (2015) in blackbuck. The medial and lateral spines were more or less same height and it tallies with the report of tiger Pandit (1994) in tiger. The condyles of proximal extremity of tibia of leopard were larger than that of dog. On caudo-

lateral aspect on the lateral condyle, there were two small facets for articulation with proximal extremity of the fibula bone.

The distal extremity of the tibia was compressed medio-laterally and had two articular facets. The present observation on the tibia of leopard coincides with the description on tibia of dog (Sisson, 1977) except that tibia of leopard as whole was more massive. The mean circumference and width of the distal extremity was 9.27 ± 0.15 cm and 3.15 ± 0.06 cm respectively (Table.01). The popliteal lines were more prominent. Proximal and distal extremity was larger. The tibial crest was thicker in comparison to that of dog (Sisson, 1977). The medial articular groove was much deeper than lateral one. Laterally, the distal extremity presented an articular facet, which articulated with distal extremity of fibula. Medial malleolous presented rough area for the attachment of collateral ligament.

The fibula of the leopard was a thin slender bone with the proximal extremity articulating with the lateral condyle of tibia, a twisted body and a lateral malleolus at its distal extremity concurred with the findings of Onwuama *et al* (2021) in lion. The shaft was irregular, flattened medio laterally and curved distally. The mean circumference of the shaft of the tibia was 2.32 ± 0.03 cm, 2.75 ± 0.04 cm and 2.45 ± 0.03 cm at its upper, middle and lower part respectively (Table.02). The shaft was thin and cylindrical in proximal third and flat in the lower $2/3^{\text{rd}}$ (Fig. No. 04). It presented three surfaces medial, lateral and caudal. The medial surface was flat and did not come in contact with tibia. Lateral surface was convex and faced laterally in upper $2/3^{\text{rd}}$. The cranial border was sharp in the upper $2/3^{\text{rd}}$. The caudal border was blunt in upper $2/3^{\text{rd}}$ and became sharp in lower $1/3^{\text{rd}}$.

The proximal extremity of the fibula was convex and compressed transversely. Laterally, there were two eminences viz. cranial and caudal separated by a vertical sulcus and resembles to that of tiger (Pandit, 1994). The mean circumference and width of the proximal extremity of the fibula was 4.75 ± 0.06 cm and 1.81 ± 0.03 cm respectively (Table.02). The proximal extremity was convex and compressed transversely. Laterally, there were two eminences viz. cranial and caudal separated by a vertical sulcus (Fig. No. 05).

The mean circumference and width of distal extremity were measured 4.82 ± 0.05 cm and 2.02 ± 0.04 cm respectively (Table.02). The distal extremity of the fibula was also compressed medio-laterally and much

Table 01. Mean and S.E. of different parameters of tibia

S. No.	Parameters	Skeleton I	Skeleton II	Skeleton III	Skeleton IV	Mean	S.E.
1.	Weight (gm)	94.81	98.23	96.67	95.18	96.22	0.78
2.	Length (cm)	21.00	24.10	23.60	22.20	22.72	0.70
3.	Shaft (cm)						
	Length	17.00	19.90	19.50	18.00	18.6	0.67
	Circumference						
	• Upper part	8.90	11.00	9.50	9.10	9.62	0.47
	• Middle part	6.40	7.10	6.70	6.50	6.67	0.15
	• Lower part	5.50	9.40	5.90	5.70	6.62	0.92
4.	Medial condyle (cm)						
	• Length	3.00	3.60	3.40	3.30	3.32	0.12
	• Width	1.50	2.00	1.70	1.60	1.70	0.10
5.	Lateral condyle (cm)						
	• Length	2.80	3.20	3.00	2.90	2.97	0.08
	• Width	1.60	2.20	2.00	1.90	1.92	0.12
6.	Proximal extremity (cm)						
	• Circumference	13.00	15.00	14.10	13.90	14.00	0.41
	• Width	4.30	5.00	4.70	4.60	4.65	0.14
7.	Distal extremity (cm)						
	• Circumference	9.00	9.70	9.30	9.10	9.27	0.15
	• Width	3.00	3.30	3.20	3.10	3.15	0.06

Table 02. Mean and S.E. of different parameters of fibula

thicker than proximal extremity and tallied with that of dog (Sisson, 1977). The medial surface on its cranial aspects had a wider articular facet articulated with the tibia and also with the fibular tarsal. There was another articular facet caudally which articulated only with fibular tarsal bone. On the lateral aspect of the extremity there was deep, vertical groove known as the sulcus malleolaris lateralis. Lateral malleolus was the distal extremity of fibula.

References

1. **Bharti, S. K. and Ishwer, S. (2020).** Morphometrical studies of tibia, fibula and lateral malleolus of the blue bull (*Boselephus tragocamelus*). *J. Ent. Zoology Studies*, **8**(2): 84-87.
2. **Getty R, Sisson and Grossman's (1975).** The Anatomy of the Domesticated Animals. [W.B. Saunders Co. Philadelphia], 5:273-296.
3. **Menon, K., and A. Kumar (1999).** Wildlife Crime. An Enforcement Guide, Wildlife Protection Society of India p 61.
4. **Onwuama, K. T., Salami, S.O., Kigir, E.S. and Jaji AZ (2021).** Gross anatomical studies on hind limb of African Lion (*Panthera leo*). *J. Vet. Res. Advances*, **3**(2): 07-12.
5. **Pandit, R. V. (1994).** Osteology of Indian tiger. Tech. Bull.No.VI., Conservator of Forest and Director, Project Tiger, Melghat, Amravati pp 29-57.
6. **Panes, V. G. and P. V. Sukhatme (1967).** *Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers*, I.C.A.R., New Delhi., p.381.
7. **Podhade, D.N. (2007).** Studies on the appendicular skeleton of leopard as an aid in wildlife forensics. M. V. Sc Thesis. JNKVV.
8. **Raghavan D. (1964).** Anatomy of ox. Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi, pp. 97-117.
9. **Ray, S. and Ray, M. (1994).** Anatomical study of tibia (*Os tibia*) and Fibula (*Os fibulae*) of leopard (*Panthera pardus*). *Indian J. Vet. Anat.*, **6**(1):46-48.
10. **Sisson, S. (1977).** The Anatomy of the Domestic Animals-II. Publ., The Macmillan Co. of India Ltd. pp.1427-1483.
11. **Snedecor, C. W. and W. G., Cochran (1967).** *Statistical Methods* 6th edn., Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., Bombay, p 593.

S. No.	Parameters	Skeleton I	Skeleton II	Skeleton III	Skeleton IV	Mean	S.E.
1.	Weight (gm)	10.37	14.29	12.38	11.31	12.08	0.42
2.	Length (cm)	19.70	22.80	21.30	20.70	21.12	0.32
3.	Shaft(cm) Length Circumference	16.60	19.50	18.10	17.50	17.92	0.60
	• Upper part	2.20	2.50	2.30	2.30	2.32	0.03
	• Middle part	2.60	3.00	2.70	2.70	2.75	0.04
	• Lower part	2.30	2.60	2.20	2.40	2.45	0.03
4.	Proximal extremity (cm) • Circumference • Width	4.40	5.00	4.90	4.70	4.75	0.06
		1.62	1.91	1.81	1.92	1.81	0.03
5.	Distal extremity (cm) • Circumference • Width	4.60	5.80	5.40	4.90	4.82	0.05
		1.86	2.27	2.03	1.92	2.02	0.04

Fig. No. 1 : Tibia

Fig. No. 2 : Tibia (Proximal extremity)

Fig. No. 3 : Tibia (Distal extremity)

Fig. No. 4 : Fibula

Fig. No. 5 : Fibula (Proximal extremity)

Fig. No. 6 : Fibula (Distal extremity)